

Demonstrating Meta strategic Knowledge of RR skills during their collaborative processing

The examples below are from the transcripts of pairs of teachers solving tasks for application with RR skills. During application, it is possible to get an impression of the meta-strategic thinking processes as expressed by teachers in making decisions to what extent a specific skill is reflected in the phenomenon. How they deal with challenges of the skill's characteristics, how they activate it and when they use it.

(1). Task transcript for applying Antinomy on living beings' open and closed blood systems.

Avi: *"Was there anything here that we used antinomy? There is a kind of comparison of similar and different here, but it is similar and different from the obvious. I do not think so. Like, I don't know how many antinomies there were here, I don't know, what do you say?"*

Nazara: *"I need to reread the question. Maybe because there are no capillaries, veins, and capillaries that return the blood in an open-heart system, can this be used as an antinomy? I think there was no antinomy here".*

Avi: *"I don't think there was an antinomy here because there is a comparison between two systems, one open and one closed, which is self-evident. We will recognize that there is no sorting here and no category, and no characteristic. There is no way to take and negate a system in relation to another. It is not relevant here. Nazara: Yes, it fits me better, but I still can't understand the difference between the skills of sorting into two categories and the antinomy. So, through the antinomy, you can sort.*

Avi: *It's a sorting, but it's also a discussion to try to characterize the different and then from what you find different to try to characterize it again, understand?"* Nazara: *"Yes, it is a complex sorting, which already includes several things".*

In the question above, the teachers were required to explain why there is a difference between two categories - open and closed blood systems. In this case, the teachers gave a good reason to exclude antinomy. The teachers need to distinguish between two similar skills of sorting and antinomy and when to use each, promoting their understanding - of what, how, and when to apply antinomy. And especially when using the skill.

(2). Task transcript for applying Antinomy in explaining the differences between homeothermic and poikilotherm creatures.

Hagit: *"We concluded that there is a lot in common regarding the components and the structure, but in the heart of reptiles, the septum is not complete compared to mammals, where the septum is complete. The inference was the role of the partition, the connection between the components, that it does not allow mixing between the blood types. The mapping was a similar functional principle, the separation of the blood. The antinomy was to find the difference when it was not to be satisfied with having or not having a septum or that the septum is complete or not but to reach something a little more principled and deeper, and this is what leads us to who can produce a high body temperature, and who depends on an external source"*.

Efi: *"This is the mapping"*.

Hagit: *"According to what I understood, it is a similar functional principle, and antinomy is that we have to find the difference between them"*.

Efrat: *"I break it down in a completely different way than what I teach so that I go for such a question, so what we do at the beginning is look at the structure of the heart of a mammal and a reptile. We look at what is similar, as if looking at what a mammal's heart looks like and what a heart looks like of a reptile and that there are two chambers and two ascents, but there is a partition in it, there is no partition in it, there is blood... I mean, really, only at the beginning. After we describe the structure of the heart of a mammal and a reptile, we refer to the function. But for the question you ask, ok, I did the coding, and I need to think about the conclusion, so in terms of this question, I think for a moment about the septum, what is the role of the septum? And as far as I'm concerned, this is the conclusion, the septum maintains, allows blood flow, and does not allow mixing between arterial and venous blood. And then, like I say, ok, and why is it so important?"*

I defined what it means to be homeothermic and poikilothermic. We have a process in the body and cellular respiration that produces body heat and consumes oxygen. So, in my phrase, what is the connection between having a partition and body heat? When there is a septum, there is no mixing of arterial and venous blood; thus, the oxygen supply in the cells and cellular respiration is possible.

When we talked about where the antinomy comes in here, I'm saying, ok, I have homeothermic animals that need a high oxygen supply to the cells. In mammals, I have a septum, which allows an increased supply of oxygen and the release of heat and maintaining a constant body temperature, then an animal is homeothermic. Then I say, ok, the reptile does not have a septum, it cannot transport oxygen in that amount, and

it cannot do high cellular respiration. It cannot maintain a constant body temperature, so it is not homeothermic or poikilothermic”.

In this example, the teachers provided an in-depth biological explanation of the functional mechanism by creating meaningful relations to the structure of the blood system. The teachers' explicit use of cognitive actions helped them apply antinomic thinking by categorically distinguishing between a homeothermic transport system versus a poikilothermic. Doing so contributed to an in-depth understanding of those scientific concepts. Furthermore, the teacher's descriptions of teaching this subject before she learned to apply the skill of antinomy in that subject showed the teacher's high level of reflective awareness. By raising significant need for an in-depth understanding of a scientific explanation that she had previously explained on a factual, superficial level (without making a connection between the structure - appearance a septum in the heart and its role in maintaining body temperature.